

IMPROVING MECHANISMS OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION BY DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN PRESCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Today's demand requires the improvement of the aesthetic education mechanisms along with the professional skills, knowledge, intelligence, and creativity of the educator. This article talks about the existing problems in improving and mastering aesthetic education by developing the educator's creativity competence.*

Keywords: *pedagogue, educator, aesthetics, creativity, competence, pedagogical skill, professional competence, functional tasks of a pedagogue, pedagogical ability, pedagogical technique, pedagogical qualimetry, pedagogical attitude.*

It is known that the scientific discoveries created by our great thinkers and scholars, the rare spiritual and cultural heritage, the highest values of our society form the basis for the formation and development of the moral and aesthetic outlook of a person.

In fact, the moral aesthetic outlook is a set of scientific, philosophical, legal, ethical, political, aesthetic, religious views and imaginations of people about the objective existence and its change and development, as a result of which the universal human ideas, values, knowledge are acquired, ideals (social, moral, aesthetic) are formed, social attitude to the Motherland, society, nation, traditions, native history and language is formed.

It should not be overlooked that the essence and importance of the moral-aesthetic worldview is determined by the scope of its influence on the socio-political, spiritual-cultural and economic development of the society, and the maturity of the youth. According to this, the moral-aesthetic worldview is developed, and the morals, knowledge, thinking, belief, scientific, religious, and ideological views, ideals, faith and will of the people, nation, we understand the people who can connect with society, interest, development, perspective of the Motherland. Also, people with a developed moral-aesthetic worldview conduct their activities in compliance with the criteria of morality, duty and responsibility, justice and truth, honesty and truthfulness, humanitarianism and philanthropy, and legal obligations accepted by the society. For this, it is important to form aesthetic education from childhood.

In order to develop aesthetic education among children of pre-school educational organization, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms of aesthetic education, first of all, among pedagogues. It is appropriate to implement this through the development of creative competence.

Ethical-aesthetic outlook of educators is required to be extremely wide, multifaceted, deep and complex in terms of essence, and it requires theoretical and practical analysis according to its content. Therefore, first of all, by clarifying the theoretical and practical aspects, similarities, integrity and differences of the concepts of "worldview", "ethics", "aesthetics", considering the essence of the phrase "ethical-aesthetic worldview", social-pedagogical phenomenon we consider it appropriate to justify it, and to develop technologies for its development in future teachers.

Because the first foundation of the educational stage begins with pre-school education. In this case, the teacher himself must be perfect in all aspects and be a creative person with a broad worldview. It is known that "worldview" is a socio-philosophical concept, which is an important category in the content of the science of philosophy and forms the basis of philosophy.

Philosophy, as a wisdom-loving science, explains worldview as a category that expresses people's views, knowledge, and thinking about the world and people, and is manifested in events and phenomena, practical activities, relationships, and their understanding. Based on this, "Worldview" is a phenomenon that expresses people's perception of reality, its change and development. So, based on worldview, a person understands himself, reality, reacts to existence, therefore, based on this, he learns his place in society, determines his goal, personal and social status based on acquired knowledge. This is a necessary condition for the formation of humanitarianism, patriotism, loyalty to national and universal values, practical assistance in preserving and improving them.

In order to further improve the mechanisms of aesthetic education in educators, it is important to develop their creative competence.

Creativity includes the organization of the educational process, the construction of a creative educational process, the development of creative potential from educational technologies, the development of a balance of different methods, knowledge and skills.

The essence of creativity is that intelligence is the mental potential of a person, and creativity is the ability to freely use this mental potential in a purposeful manner. In order to fully understand the general nature of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is necessary to first understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity". The concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows:

Creativity (lat., ing. "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) - creative ability that characterizes the readiness of an individual to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor.

Usually, the ability of pedagogues to have creativity is provided, shaped and gradually improved and developed by striving to solve pedagogical problems, conducting scientific research or scientific projects and achieving mutual creative cooperation.

When organizing creative activities, a teacher should pay attention to solving problematic issues, analyzing problematic situations, and also creating creative products of a pedagogical nature. While solving problematic issues and situations, the pedagogue's creative approach to finding a solution to the problem helps the development of emotional volitional qualities. By putting problematic issues in front of him, the pedagogue confronts evidence that contradicts his existing knowledge and life experiences. As a result, he feels the need to work on himself, study independently. Modern education requires educators and pedagogues working in all types of educational institutions to be creative.

It is necessary to pay special attention to solving problematic issues, analyzing problematic situations, as well as creating creative products of a pedagogical nature when organizing creative activities of a teacher.

The complexity of organizing and managing the creative process is that not only conscious, but also subconscious concepts of creative individuality appear in it, and at the same time, aesthetic education is formed.

Development of moral-aesthetic worldview in future teachers, deepening of legal democratic changes in the Republic, beautiful socio-economic life in the conditions of formation of foundations of civil society, ideal society and foreign ideological views and It would be correct to say that it is a socio-pedagogical phenomenon that represents the educational process aimed at forming new people who can fight against ideas.

Based on this, it can be said that the development of moral and aesthetic worldview acquires an important pedagogical value, both in forming the worldview of well-rounded people, and in training the builders of a perfect society and experts who have a deep understanding of the national ideology. Because a person with a developed moral and aesthetic worldview preserves nature, adheres to universal values, raises national consciousness, contributes to the development of the country, and fully fulfills his duties and responsibilities.

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